

A NOTE ON THE SYNTHESIS OF α -*n*-DECYL-
 α -ETHYLSUCCINIC ACID

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In course of the investigations on phthioic acid, obtained from *M. Tuberculosis*, Robinson and his collaborators failed to condense ethyl cyanoacetate with decylethyl ketone (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1942, 488). The above condensation has been carried out successfully according to the following conditions and thus α -decyl- α -ethylsuccinic acid has been prepared.

Decylethyl ketone was prepared following the method of Cason (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1942, 64, 1106). To the cold Grignard complex, prepared from ethyl iodide (41 g.), ether (150 c.c.) and magnesium (6.5 g.), cadmium chloride (25 g.) was added in portion and shaken. After some time ether was removed by heating on the water-bath and benzene (50 c.c., thiophene-free) was added and the benzene distilled off. Next the content of the flask was cooled and shaken vigorously with benzene (100 c.c.) to disperse the solid cake at the bottom of the flask. A solution of the acid chloride of undecic acid (35.8 g.) in benzene (40 c.c.) was added drop by drop to the cold reaction mixture with constant shaking. After the completion of the addition it was refluxed for 1 hour. It was next decomposed with iced dilute sulphuric acid and exhausted with benzene. The residue, left after removal of benzene, was refluxed for 2 hours with 5% alcoholic solution of potassium hydroxide (90 c.c.) and worked up in the usual way, b. p. 132-34°/10.5 mm., yield 22.8 g.

The above ketone (22.8 g.), ethyl cyanoacetate (12.9 c.c.), ammonium acetate (4.46 g.), acetic acid (5.5 c.c.) and benzene (23 c.c.) were refluxed following the modified condition of Cope (*ibid.*, 1941, 63, 3452), b. p. 192°/6 mm., yield 18 g. (Found : C, 73.29 ; H, 10.13. $C_{18}H_{31}O_2N$ requires C, 73.37 ; H, 10.58 per cent).

Diethyl α -Decyl- α -ethylsuccinate.—A solution of potassium cyanide (7.93 g.) in water (43.1 c.c.) was added dropwise to a solution of the above unsaturated cyano-ester (ethyl 2-cyano-3-ethyl- Δ^2 -tridecoate, 18 g.) in alcohol (70 c.c.) and water (3.6 c.c.) with constant shaking. Next the content of the flask and a mixture of concentrated HCl (9.6 c.c.) and water (6.8 c.c.) were efficiently cooled in ice for 40 minutes. Then the acid solution was added drop by drop into the flask which was shaken constantly. The reaction mixture was left for another $\frac{1}{2}$ hour and then poured into iced dilute HCl, exhausted with ether which was then driven off. The residue was refluxed with concentrated sulphuric acid (75 c.c.) and water (75 c.c.) for 12 hours. It was then worked up in the usual way and subjected to alkaline hydrolysis by refluxing with aqueous solution of KOH (45 g., 25%) for 60 hours in

order to free it from nitrogen. It was worked as usual and the residue after removal of solvent was dried in vacuum. The dried residue was refluxed with alcohol (50 c.c.) and sulphuric acid (7 c.c.) for 70 hours, b. p. $170^{\circ}/4$ mm., yield 16 g. (Found : C, 69.9 ; H, 11.1. $C_{20}H_{38}O_4$ requires C, 70.17 ; H, 11.11 per cent).

α -Ethyl- α -n-decylsuccinic Acid.—The above ester was hydrolysed with 20% ethanolic KOH and worked up as usual. The crude acid was thrice crystallised from small amounts of glacial acetic acid, m.p. $84-86^{\circ}$. (Found : C, 66.97 ; H, 10.19. $C_{18}H_{30}O_4$ requires C, 67.13 ; H, 10.48 per cent).

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